

Evaluation of Exact Sum of Generalized Infinite Series

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Abstract: The manuscript investigates techniques for precisely evaluating the exact sum of generalized infinite series. This manuscript delves into the intricate process of deriving a generating function, rigorously establishing the convergence criteria for series, and subsequently determining the exact summation of generalized series. Through systematic analysis and application of mathematical frameworks, it explores various techniques to achieve precise summations. The study contributes significantly to the understanding of infinite series evaluation, offering insights into theoretical foundations and practical methodologies.

Key words: Infinite series, convergence, summability, Alternating series, Generalization

I. INTRODUCTION

In the February 1995 issue of Math Horizons, I. Fisher presented the following problem [1]: $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k(k+1)}$

and $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^2} = \frac{\pi^2}{6}$, it follows that $1 < \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k(k+\frac{1}{2})} < \frac{\pi^2}{6}$

Based on established results, the exact value of the convergent sum can be determined.

Also, Consider the series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+a)(k+b)} = \frac{1}{a-b} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{(k+b)} - \frac{1}{(k+a)} \right]$ where $a \neq b$ and neither a nor

b is a negative integer. Sums of this nature frequently emerge in problem domains related to Quantum Field Theory (p. 89, [2]).

This paper presents a solution method that enables the precise calculation of values for a wide range of convergent series.

This manuscript delves into deriving a generating function, establishing the convergence of series, and subsequently determining the exact sum of a generalized series.

II. MAIN RESULTS

We are familiar with the convergent alternating series $\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k(k+1)}$. In this section of this paper, we

generalize it as $H(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)}$ and

$F(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)}$ for positive integers $a, b,$ and c . Following this,

we'll prove its convergence and determine its exact sum.

The generating function serves as a powerful tool in encapsulating information about the series in a concise mathematical form. Let's proceed with deriving it.

Initially, we derive the series $H(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)}$ by using gamma function as follows:

For $a, b, c > 0$ consider the series

$$(1) \quad H(a,b,c) = \frac{1}{c!} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(ak+b)\Gamma(c+1)}{\Gamma(ak+b+c+1)}$$

The preceding series is expressed by the integral as follows:

$$(2) \quad H(a,b,c) = \frac{1}{c!} \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{\Gamma(ak+b)\Gamma(c+1)}{\Gamma(ak+b+c+1)} = \frac{1}{c!} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b-1}(1-t)^c}{1-t^a} dt$$

When $a, b, c > 0$ are integers the above series (2) is given by

$$(3) \quad H(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)} = \frac{1}{c!} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b-1}(1-t)^c}{1-t^a} dt$$

In the forthcoming theorem, we will establish the convergence of our series.

Theorem 2.1:

The series $H(a,b,c)$ is convergent, where positive integers $a, b,$ and c .

Proof:

For positive integers $a, b,$ and c the series $H(a,b,c)$ is

$$H(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)} = O\left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+1)^{c+1}}\right)$$

As the c is any positive integer, $c+1 \geq 2$

Therefore, the series $\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(k+1)^{c+1}}$ is convergent.

Hence, the series $H(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)}$ is convergent.

Next, we contemplate whether obtaining the exact sum of the series in equation (3) is feasible. Indeed, a positive result emerges. To calculate the exact sum of the aforementioned series, we must assess the value of the final integral in equation (3).

To achieve this, let's examine the integral for arbitrary positive integers $a, b,$ and c as follows:

$$(4) \quad I(a,b,c) = \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b-1}(1-t)^c}{1-t^a} dt$$

Therefore, deriving from equations (3) and (4), we obtain:

$$(5) \quad H(a,b,c) = \frac{1}{c!} I(a,b,c)$$

We can express equation (4) as follows

$$(6) \quad I(a, b, c) = \sum_{n=0}^c \left((-1)^n \binom{c}{n} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b+n-1}}{1-t^a} dt \right)$$

To evaluate the integral mentioned in equation (6), we need to compute the last integral in the same equation, indicated as follows

$$(7) \quad I_{a,b}(n) = \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b+n-1}}{1-t^a} dt$$

So, equation (6) can be expressed as follows

$$(8) \quad I(a, b, c) = \sum_{n=0}^c \left((-1)^n \binom{c}{n} I_{a,b}(n) \right)$$

By evaluating the integral in (7), we can determine the exact sum of our series in equation (3). However, to evaluate this integral, two cases arise: when a is an odd integer and when a is an even integer. This implies that we obtain the exact sum of the series in equation (3) in two parts: one when a is an odd integer and the other when a is an even integer. $\square$

Theorem 2.2:

For even integer $a > 0$ and positive integers b and c , with $b+n < a$ and $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, c\}$ the series

$$(9) \quad H(a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots(ak+b+c)}$$

Sums to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{c!} \sum_{n=0}^c (-1)^n \binom{c}{n} \left(\frac{(-1)^{b+c+1}}{a} \ln 2 - \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \left(\cos\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2 \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{a}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\ & + \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{k\pi}{a} \right) \sin\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Proof:

To establish this theorem, it suffices to assess the integral (7) for even integers $a > 0$. To do so, employ integral formula 4 of 2.146 [p.76, [5]] in equation (7), resulting in:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{a,b}(n) = & \frac{1}{a} \{ (-1)^{b+c+1} \ln(1+t) - \ln(1-t) \} - \frac{1}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(1 - 2t \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right) + t^2\right) \\ & + \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \operatorname{arctg}\left(\frac{t - \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right)}\right) \Bigg|_0^1, \text{ where } b+n < a \end{aligned}$$

Simplifying the equation above, we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{a,b}(n) &= \frac{(-1)^{b+c+1}}{a} \ln 2 - \frac{1}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2\left(1 - \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right)\right)\right) \\
 &+ \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \left(\operatorname{arctg}\left(\frac{1 - \cos\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right)}\right) - \operatorname{arctg}\left(-\cot\left(\frac{2k\pi}{a}\right)\right)\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

, where $b + n < a$

Further simplifying equation (9) for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{a-2}{2}$ yields:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{a,b}(n) &= \frac{(-1)^{b+c+1}}{a} \ln 2 - \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \left(\cos\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2 \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{a}\right)\right)\right) \\
 &+ \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{k\pi}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

, where $b + n < a$

Combining equations (8) and (11), we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I(a, b, c) &= \sum_{n=0}^c (-1)^n \binom{c}{n} \left(\frac{(-1)^{b+c+1}}{a} \ln 2 - \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \left(\cos\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2 \sin\left(\frac{k\pi}{a}\right)\right)\right) \right. \\
 &\left. + \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-2}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{k\pi}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{2k(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

, where $b + n < a$

Thus, by utilizing equations (5) and (11), we attain the sum of our series $H(a, b, c)$. □

Likewise, in the upcoming theorem, we can determine the exact sum of the series $H(a, b, c)$ by utilizing integral formula 3 of 2.146 [p.76, [5]] in equation (7) when $a > 0$ is an odd integer.

Theorem 2.3:

For odd integer $a > 0$ and positive integers b and c , with $b + n < a$ and $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, c\}$ the series

$$(12) \quad H(a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(ak + b)(ak + b + 1)\dots(ak + b + c)}$$

Sums to

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\frac{1}{c!} \sum_{n=0}^c \frac{2(-1)^{b+1}}{a} \binom{c}{n} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-1}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2 \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{2a}\right)\right) \right. \\
 &\left. + \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-1}{2}} \left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{2a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

□

Next, we will establish the convergence of the alternating series $F(a, b, c)$, followed by deriving its generating function and evaluating its exact sum

Theorem 2.4:

The series $F(a,b,c)$ is absolutely convergent, where positive integers a , b , and c .

Proof:

According to Theorem 3.1.1, for positive integers a , b , and c the series $H(a,b,c)$ is convergent. Consequently, it follows that the alternating series $F(a,b,c)$ is absolutely convergent.

□

Similarly to the series $H(a,b,c)$ we can derive the integral form for the alternating series $F(a,b,c)$ as follows:

$$(13) \quad F(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)} = \frac{1}{c!} \sum_{n=0}^c \left((-1)^n \binom{c}{n} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b+n-1}}{1+t^a} dt \right)$$

By evaluating the final integral in (14), we can determine the exact sum of our alternating series. However, to evaluate this integral, two cases arise: when a is an odd integer and when a is an even integer.

Theorem 2.5:

For even integer $a > 0$ and positive integers b and c , with $b+n < a$ and $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\dots\dots, c\}$ the series

$$(14) \quad F(a,b,c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(ak+b)(ak+b+1)\dots\dots\dots(ak+b+c)}$$

Sums to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{c!} \sum_{n=0}^c \frac{2(-1)^{n+1}}{a} \binom{c}{n} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2 \sin\left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{2a}\right)\right) \right) \\ & - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{(2k-1)\pi}{2a} \right) \sin\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \end{aligned}$$

Proof:

To establish this theorem, it suffices to assess the last integral of (13) for even integers $a > 0$. To do so, employ integral formula 1 of 2.146 [p.76, [5]] in equation (13), resulting in:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_0^1 \frac{t^{b+n-1}}{1+t^a} dt &= \frac{-1}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(1 - 2t \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{a}\right) + t^2\right) \\ &+ \frac{2}{a} \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a}{2}} \sin\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \operatorname{arrctg}\left(\frac{t - \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{a}\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{a}\right)}\right) \Bigg|_0^1 \end{aligned}$$

, where $b+n < a$

Simplifying above equation for $1 \leq k \leq \frac{a}{2}$ and substituting in (13) we get exact sum of desired series in equation (14). □

Similarly, in the subsequent theorem, we can derive the exact sum of the series when $a > 0$ is an odd integer by utilizing integral formula 2 of 2.146 from [p.76, [5]] in equation (13).

Theorem 2.6:

For odd integer $a > 0$ and positive integers b and c , with $b + n < a$ and $n \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, c\}$ the series

$$(15) \quad F(a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^k}{(ak + b)(ak + b + 1)\dots(ak + b + c)}$$

Sums to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{1}{c!} \sum_{n=0}^c \frac{2(-1)^{n+1}}{a} \binom{c}{n} \left(\frac{(-1)^{b+n+1}}{2} \ln 2 - \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-1}{2}} \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \cdot \ln\left(2 \cos\left(\frac{(2k-1)\pi}{2a}\right)\right) \right. \\ & \left. + \sum_{k=1}^{\frac{a-1}{2}} \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \frac{(2k-1)\pi}{a}\right) \sin\left(\frac{(2k-1)(b+n)\pi}{a}\right) \right) \end{aligned}$$

□

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